

The impact of managerial coaching on employee job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intention in transportation and logistics companies in Vietnam

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8125088>

ABSTRACT

Organizations these days need to face to the force of speedy environmental changes as well as the much more severe competition from others. Employee job satisfaction and Organizational Commitment are among the most important and talked about job attitudes that organizations are seeking for. According to Statistics figure of Vietnam Ministry of Industry and Trade, there are about 23,000 companies working in this field in 2016 but more than 90% of them are small and super small companies. In this study, 400 questionnaires were sent out and 148 valid responses were collected for the further analysis to investigate the impact of managerial coaching on employee job satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and turnover intention in logistics and transportation companies in Vietnam. The results of this research are consistent with literature review of Managerial Coaching and favorable outcomes managerial coaching could generate for employees working in transportation and logistics companies in Vietnam. It did provide further empirical evidence of managerial coaching away from Western Country. In particular, it strengthens the theoretical evidences of the outcomes of managerial coaching under Vietnam context, in companies working in logistics and transportation industry.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Organizational commitment, Turnover intention, Logistics, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Organizations these days need to face to the force of speedy environmental changes as well as the much more severe competition from others. These changes claim the new approach to leaderships (Park, 2007) and lead to numerous challenges for Human resource management (Ye et al., 2016). Recently, line managers and supervisors are carrying out some kinds of tasks that used to be performed by Human resource experts (Hall & Torrington, 1998). Organizations are expecting managers to do more than merely supervising work (Pousa, 2018), indeed, organizations have expected direct managers to coach their subordinates to help them grow and enable them to learn (Thornhill & Saunders, 1998). This kind of new approach has been widely known as managerial coaching. From 1990s, managerial coaching has been earning more and more popularity among organizations (Park, 2007).

Managerial Coaching, being illustrated as “an effective managerial practice that helps employees learn and become effective” (Kim, 2010; Ellinger & Bostrom, 1999; Peterson & Hicks, 1996; Evered & Selman, 1989). Managerial coaching has been considered as one of the central leadership skills and the important solution for the success of employees and organizations (Clutterbuck, 2008; Gilley, Shelton, & Gilley, 2011; Kim & Egan, 2011). Take Google as an instance, this technology giant determined that a great manager should be a good coach (Garvin, 2013). In addition, employees also seek for more coaching from their managers and think that managerial coaching may bring about their development and competitiveness of the organizations (Longenecker & Neubert, 2005).

Despite the emerging importance of Managerial Coaching over the last two decades, Beatie et al. (2014) still claimed for more Managerial Coaching literature outside Western countries. Furthermore, according to Ye et al. (2016), more managerial coaching behaviors are exhibited by the managers in collectivistic cultures than those in individualistic cultures. It could be inferred that the collectivistic cultures in a non-Western country may be the ideal environments for the managerial coaching to be performed. According to the culture research carried out by Hofstede, Vietnam is defined as a collectivistic culture so Vietnamese companies may be the good environment for managers to perform their managerial coaching.

Employee job satisfaction and Organizational Commitment are among the most important and talked about job attitudes that organizations are seeking for. Especially, gaining employee job satisfaction is even considered to be the crucial outcome by an effective manager (Schermerhorn et al., 2010). Achieving high level of employees’ job satisfaction and Organizational Commitment is believed to be a way of enhancing the performance among

employees which contributes well for the development of organizations. In addition, one of the employees' behaviors that organizations also pay much attention to is employee's turnover intention. While it is obvious that high rate of turnover could be very expensive for organizations due to the loss of experiences, high cost of recruiting and training new employees (Schermerhorn et al., 2010); earlier identifying the turnover intention of employees could help to reduce the actual leave as well as to save cost for organizations. More than that, recently, as "quitting trend", which may be the consequence of the rapid increase in the number of available jobs in Vietnam, has become more and more popular among Vietnamese young generation; lowering the turnover level could become a constant headache for organizations to solve. Therefore, studying about the new factor which could increase employees' job satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and decrease turnover intentions like managerial coaching is an essential thing to do.

Transportation and logistics industry of Vietnam has been witnessing the fast period of growth thanks to the speedy growth of commercial activities as well as the support from policies. In 2018, the figure of 12% was recorded for the growth of transportation and logistics industry (Vietnam Ministry of Industry and Trade, 2018). The Logistics Performance Index (LPI), a reliable measure for national logistics capability published by World Bank in 2018 shows that Vietnam was ranked 36th out of 160 ranked countries, ranked 3rd out of 11 nations of ASEAN and especially, hold the first position among emerging markets despite the fact that this industry is still new in Vietnam. Vietnam's ranking has increased 14 places since 2018 which could present for the strong and fast development of this industry. Furthermore, the revenue comes from this industry has contributed 2 to 4% to Vietnamese GDP and has the estimated growth of 18 – 20% per year, three times larger than the developing speed of national economy (which was 6.5% in 2018) (Vietnam Logistics Report, 2018). Vietnam Government Audit newspaper reported that 73 percent of transportation and logistics companies operating in Vietnam were optimistic that 2019 would be the exploding year for transportation & logistics industry with the growth of 2 figures.

According to Statistics figure of Vietnam Ministry of Industry and Trade, there are about 23,000 companies working in this field in 2016 but more than 90% of them are small and super small companies. In spite of its huge potential and quick growth, the lack of well-educated labor force is among the 3 biggest challenges of this industry. Since it is a quite new industry, the ability of human working in this field is still limited. It is recorded that only 5 to 7% of the work force working in transportation and logistics industry is well-educated (Vietnam Logistics Report, 2018). This limited ability leads to the need for more coaching to improve its ability. On the other hand, the labor force of this industry is mostly young people who are considered to be "hard to satisfy" and "easy to quit".

Over the period of 20 years, the number of managerial coaching studies has risen considerably (Grant, 2011). However, according to Beattie et al. (2014), there still remains a significant gap in the Managerial Coaching literature away from Western countries. For that reason, more studies about managerial coaching should still be conducted under the circumstances of Asian countries like Vietnam. Thus, this study is aimed to study the influence of managerial coaching on employee job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intentions in transportation & logistics companies in Vietnam.

2. Literature review

From 1880s, the word "coach" which referred to "one who instructs, trains, or guides players or performers (or team thereof) in some particular activities or endeavor" did appear in the dictionary (Evered & Selman, 1989). At that time, coaching was mainly used in sports where coaches would coach players in some games like golf, tennis or ice skating to help them get the better performances. Coaching initially came to management field since 1950s (Evered & Selman, 1989). At that time, coaching was considered as one among the duties of supervisors to enhance their followers in form of "master-apprentice" relation. There had been some articles trying to translate coaching in sports into managerial situations since the middle of 1970s. Several typical techniques used in sports coaching such as how to "motivate people, train them in job skill or improve management development" were attempted to apply into business context. There are various ways to define coaching in organizations based on the different viewpoints (Hamlin, Ellinger & Beattie, 2009). The definitions of managerial coaching could be referred based on the definitions of coaching. Thus, managerial coaching is the coaching being performed by managers (Kim et al. 2013). In fact, the concept of Hierarchical coaching, where the line managers actively involve in coaching their direct subordinates, is the most popular and familiar form of managerial coaching which have been studied widely by scholars (Kim et al. 2013). For the purpose of this study, managerial coaching will be defined in form of hierarchical coaching and according to the developmental perspective based on the definition of Heslin et al. (2006). The impact of Managerial Coaching on Employee Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention will be framed by the Organization Support Theory followed by Perceived Supervisor Support. Since Managerial Coaching is considered as the organization support, employee will response this perceived supervisor support by higher job satisfaction, higher Organizational Commitment and lower turnover intention (Eisenberger et al., 2002; Stamper & Johlke, 2003; Stinglhamber & Vandenberghe, 2003). In fact, there have been some studies about managerial Coaching did find the empirical evidence of the impact of managerial coaching and employee satisfaction, employee Organizational Commitment and employee turnover intention.

According to Job Descriptive Index, quality of the supervision is one among five of the components of Employee Job satisfaction so it is another theoretical evidence supporting that the managerial coaching will impact on Employee Job Satisfaction. Ellinger et al. (2003) carried out a study of 438 employees working in warehouse and found a significantly positive relation between managerial coaching and Employee Job Satisfaction. Kim et al. 2013 also found the empirical evidence that managerial coaching had the significantly positive impact on employee job satisfaction. Managerial coaching could impact on Employee Organizational Commitment in several different ways. First of all, for employees who always want to develop themselves, managerial coaching may likely make organization become a more attractive place to work for, thus enhancing organizational commitment among employees (Kidd & Smewing, 2001). In addition, managerial coaching's competencies such as facilitation or inspiration could create the trust with managers and this may strengthen the feeling of commitment among employees in organization (Meyer & Allen, 1997). In particular, some

scholars did study on the direct impact of managerial coaching on employee organizational commitment and their results are consistent. Park (2007) conducted an empirical study in technology industry and investigated that managerial coaching significantly positively impact on employee Organizational Commitment. Kim et al. (2013) did also prove the significantly positive relation between managerial coaching and Affective Organizational Commitment among Korean employees. Managerial Coaching is believed to enhance the trust and improve relation between subordinates and line managers (Park, 2007). Managerial Coaching is also a predictor for Employee's satisfaction with supervisors (Kim et al., 2013). While a good subordinate-supervisor relation and satisfaction of supervisors are proved to be the determinants of lowering turnover intention among employees, it can refer that managerial coaching could negatively impact on employee's turnover intention. In the empirical study in technology companies, Park (2007) did found one of the results of managerial coaching was to reduce employee turnover intention. Employee Job Satisfaction was proved to be the significant predictor of Affective Organizational Commitment by many authors (Meyer & Allen, 1997; Liou & Nyhan, 1994; Romzek, 1989; Meyer, 2002; Kim et al., 2013). In addition, Schermerhorn et al. (2010) suggested that employee job satisfaction impacted considerably on withdrawal behaviors. In particular, they claimed that dissatisfied employees tended to quit or would like to quit their organizations while employees who were more satisfied tended to stay still with their organizations.

Based on the literature review, the conceptual framework was developed as followed.

Figure 1: The research framework

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Managerial Coaching significantly positively impacts on Employee Job Satisfaction

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Managerial Coaching significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Managerial Coaching negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Employee Job Satisfaction significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment

Hypothesis 5 (H5): Employee Job Satisfaction significantly negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention

3. Methodology

This study is carried out to investigate the impact of managerial coaching on employee job satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and turnover intention in logistics and transportation companies in Vietnam. The targeted participants of this research are employees who are currently working in logistics and transportation companies in Vietnam. The targeted participants were found from the opened or closed groups of employees who are working in logistics and transportation companies in social network of Facebook. Their contact information such as electronic mail addresses or online personal sites were found and used for the purpose of this research. The online survey questionnaires were sent to the targeted participants of this study along with the introduction of the research. There are two phases of Data Collection Procedure. At first, a small pilot test was carried out. About 10 participants are included in that pilot test. The purpose of this pilot test is to make sure that every question in the questionnaire could be easily understandable and clear. After that, some corrections are made before the final online questionnaires are used in the second phase of data collection procedures. In the second phase of data collection procedures, the online questionnaires with research introduction were sent to the targeted participants via their emails or online personal site. The data collected through the data Collection procedures will be processed by SPSS Statistics Software (version 20.0) by IBM groups. Firstly, the reliability test by Cronbach's Alpha test will be carried out to test the reliability of measured instruments for four of the variables used in this study. Secondly, the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) will be run to let the test group the analyzing factors based on the actual data. Thirdly, Pearson Correlation test will be conducted to investigate if there are valid correlations between independent variable and dependent variables. Finally, the data will be processed by linear regression to test the building hypotheses of this research.

4. Results and findings

4.1 Demographic information of respondents

About 400 questionnaires were sent out and 148 valid responses were collected for the further analysis. The Managerial Coaching is measured by the 10-item scale developed by Heslin et al. (2006) based on three main categories namely guidance, facilitation and inspiration. The sample measured instruments are “My manager provides guidance regarding performance expectation” (Guidance); “My manager facilitates creative thinking to help solve problems” (Facilitation); “My manager supports me in taking on new challenges” (Inspiration). Employee Job Satisfaction is measured by the 3-item scale developed by Cammann et al. (1983). The samples for these measured instruments are “All in all, I am satisfied with my job” and “In general, I like working at my current job”. 6-item scale used for measuring Employee Affective Organizational Commitment is the work of Meyer and Allen (1997). The measured instrument samples are “3.1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization” and “I do not feel like “part of the family” at my organization” and “I do not feel “emotionally attached” to this organization”. Finally, the employee Turnover intention is measured by 5-item scale developed by Wayne et al. (1997). Some samples for this measured scale are “I am actively looking for a job outside this company” and “I’m seriously thinking about quitting my job”.

Table 1: Demographic information of respondents

	Frequency	Ratio (%)
Gender		
Female	91	61.49%
Male	57	38.51%
Other	0	0.00%
Age		
Under 30	97	65.54%
30 to 45	48	32.43%
Over 45 to 60	3	2.03%
Over 60	0	0.00%
Working time		
Under 1 year	32	21.62%
1 to 3 years	64	43.24%
Over 3 to 5 years	20	13.51%
More than 5 years	32	21.62%

Table 2: Gender of respondents’ direct managers

	Frequency	Ratio
Manager's gender		
Female	47	31.76%
Male	100	67.57%
Other (Both male and female)	1	0.68%

It could be seen from the two above tables that most of the respondents are female and they count for about 61.49%. However, the male managers seem to be dominant while it is recorded around 67.57% of the respondents’ direct managers are male. In addition, the age of respondents is quite low when people who are under 30 years old count for more than 65% and 32.43% is the figure recorded for 30-to-45- year-old respondents.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

As being shown in the table 3, there are 24 items which will be studied by the responses collected from 148 respondents. The average values of managerial coaching, employee job satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and turnover intentions are 3.89, 3.64, 3.41 and 2.88 respectively. Besides, there are 5 reversed items namely JS2, AC3, AC4, AC6, TI5.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Abb.	Items	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max	N
MC1	"1.1. My manager provides guidance regarding performance expectation"	3.96	0.81	2.00	5.00	148
MC2	"1.2. My manager help me to analyse my performance"	3.86	0.83	1.00	5.00	148
MC3	"1.3. My manager provides constructive feedback regarding areas for improvement"	3.91	0.93	1.00	5.00	148
MC4	"1.4. My manager offers useful suggestions regarding how I can improve my performance"	3.96	0.89	1.00	5.00	148
MC5	"1.5. My manager acts as a sounding board for me to develop my ideas"	3.79	0.99	1.00	5.00	148
MC6	"1.6. My manager facilitates creative thinking to help solve problems"	3.83	0.94	1.00	5.00	148
MC7	"1.7. My manager encourages me to explore and try out new alternatives"	3.75	0.93	1.00	5.00	148
MC8	"1.8. My manager expresses confidence that I can develop and improve"	4.00	0.90	1.00	5.00	148
MC9	"1.9. My manager encourages me to continuously develop and improve"	3.99	0.93	1.00	5.00	148
MC10	"1.10. My manager supports me in taking on new challenges"	3.89	0.93	1.00	5.00	148
MCA	Average		0.68	1.30	5.00	148
JS1	"2.1. All in all, I am satisfied with my job"	3.60	0.80	2.00	5.00	148
JS2	"2.2. In general, I do not like my job ®"	3.67	0.87	1.00	5.00	148
JS3	"2.3. In general, I like working at my current job"	3.65	0.92	1.00	5.00	148
JSA	Average	3.64	0.82	1.33	5.00	148
AC1	"3.1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization"	3.14	1.03	1.00	5.00	148
AC2	"3.2. I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own"	3.41	0.95	1.00	5.00	148
AC3	"3.3. I do not feel like 'part of the family' at my organization ®"	3.49	0.90	1.00	5.00	148
AC4	"3.4. I do not feel 'emotionally attached' to this organization ®"	3.64	0.93	1.00	5.00	148
AC5	"3.5. This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me"	3.51	0.94	1.00	5.00	148
AC6	"3.6. I do not feel a strong sense of belong to my organization ®"	3.30	0.94	1.00	5.00	148
ACA	Average	3.41	0.82	1.00	5.00	148
TI1	"4.1. I am actively looking for a job outside this company"	2.72	1.16	1.00	5.00	148
TI2	"4.2. As soon as I can find a better job, I will leave this company"	3.07	1.19	1.00	5.00	148
TI3	"4.3. I'm seriously thinking about quitting my job"	2.82	1.25	1.00	5.00	148
TI4	"4.4. I often think about quitting my job at this company"	2.84	1.20	1.00	5.00	148
TI5	"4.5. I think I will be at this company 5 years from now ®"	3.07	1.16	1.00	5.00	148
TIA	Average	2.88	1.01	1.00	5.00	148

4.3 Correlation Analysis

The analysis result shows us that Managerial Coaching has positive correlations with Employee Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment when the Pearson Correlation results are 0.402, 0.386 respectively and the significance is smaller than 0.05. There is a very strong correlation between Employee Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment and the Pearson correlation for these 2 factors are 0.607 (significance is much smaller than 0.05). Employee Turnover Intentions has the negative correlations with the rest three factors supported by the smaller-than-0.05 significance.

Table 4: Pearson correlation statistic summary

		MCA	JSA	ACA	TIA
MCA	Pearson Correlation	1	.402**	.386**	-.191*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.020
	N	148	148	148	148
JSA	Pearson Correlation	.402**	1	.607**	-.350**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	148	148	148	148
ACA	Pearson Correlation	.386**	.607**	1	-.424**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	148	148	148	148
TIA	Pearson Correlation	-.191*	-.350**	-.424**	1

Sig. (2-tailed)	.020	.000	.000	
N	148	148	148	148

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

4.4 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Testing hypothesis 1: Managerial coaching significantly positively impacts on Job Satisfaction

Table 5: Coefficients and Significance of hypothesis 1

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.858	.312		5.961	.000	1.242	2.474		
1 MCA	.470	.089	.402	5.301	.000	.295	.646	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: JSA

The standardized Coefficient of Managerial Coaching in this hypothesis is 0.402 with the very small p-value (smaller than 0.05 – 5%). It means that Managerial Coaching significantly positively impacts on Employee Job Satisfaction.

Testing hypothesis 2: Managerial coaching significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment

Table 6: Coefficients and Significance of hypothesis 2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.802	.326		5.522	.000	1.157	2.447		
1 MCA	.469	.093	.386	5.050	.000	.286	.653	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: ACA

The standardized Coefficient of Managerial Coaching in this hypothesis is 0.386 with the very small p-value (smaller than 0.05 – 5%). It means that Managerial Coaching significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment.

Testing hypothesis 3: Managerial coaching negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention

Table 7: Coefficients and Significance of hypothesis 3

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	3.547	.407		8.725	.000	2.743	4.350		
1 MCA	-.272	.116	-.191	-2.346	.020	-.500	-.043	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: TIA

The standardized Coefficient of Managerial Coaching in this hypothesis is -0.191 with the small p-value (smaller than 0.05 – 5%). It means that Managerial Coaching negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention.

Testing hypothesis 4: Employee Job Satisfaction significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment

Table 8: Coefficients and Significance of hypothesis 4

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.223	.245		4.997	.000	.740	1.707		
1 JSA	.630	.068	.607	9.220	.000	.495	.765	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: ACA

The standardized Coefficient of Employee Job Satisfaction in this hypothesis is 0.607 with the very small p-value (smaller than 0.05 – 5%). It means that Employee Job Satisfaction significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment.

Testing hypothesis 5: Employee Job Satisfaction significantly negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention

Table 8: Coefficients and Significance of hypothesis 5

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	4.093	.338		12.118	.000	3.425	4.760		
	JSA	-.426	.094	-.350	-4.512	.000	-.612	-.239	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: TIA

The standardized Coefficient of Employee Job Satisfaction in this hypothesis is -0.350 with the very small p-value (smaller than 0.05 – 5%). It means that Employee Job Satisfaction significantly negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention.

Table 4.11: The results of multiple linear regression.

Hypotheses	Results
Hypothesis 1 (H1): Managerial coaching significantly positively impacts on Job Satisfaction	Positive
Hypothesis 2 (H2): Managerial coaching significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment	Positive
Hypothesis 3 (H3): Managerial coaching negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention	Negative
Hypothesis 4 (H4): Employee Job Satisfaction significantly positively impacts on Employee Organizational Commitment	Positive
Hypothesis 5 (H5): Employee Job Satisfaction significantly negatively impacts on Employee Turnover Intention	Negative

Figure 2: Research framework after testing

5. Results and Discussion

The research did study about the impact of managerial coaching on employee job satisfaction, employee organizational commitment and turnover intention and also study the relationships among employee job performance, Organizational Commitment and turnover intention of employees working in logistics and transportation companies in Vietnam. The descriptive results suggest that the employees in the survey scored managerial coaching of their direct managers high points with the average score of 3.98 per 5. The average scores for their job satisfactions and affective Organizational Commitment are quite high and get 3.64 and 3.41 points respectively. The study participants showed an average intention of turnover, which is 2.88 points in average. The deeper results of the study’s analysis support all the hypotheses given in the Literature and the results are consistent with what other authors like Kim et al. (2013), Park. (2007), Ellinger et al. (2003) and Allen and Meyer (1997) found out. In particular, there are significantly positive impacts of managerial coaching on Employee job satisfaction and employee Organizational Commitment while the relationship between managerial coaching and employee job satisfaction is a little bit stronger with coefficient of 0.402 compared to the coefficient of 0.386 collected when running regression model between managerial coaching and employee affective Organizational Commitment. Moreover, the result of this study also presents the significantly negative impact of managerial coaching on employee turnover intention with the coefficient of -0.191. In addition, the last two hypotheses which study about the impact of Employee Job Satisfaction on Employee Affective Organizational Commitment and Employee turnover intention are also supported. Employee Job Satisfaction significantly positively impacts Employee affective Organizational Commitment with the coefficient of 0.607 while significantly negatively impacts employee turnover intention of -0.350.

The results of this research are consistent with literature review of Managerial Coaching and favorable outcomes managerial coaching could generate for employees working in transportation and logistics companies in Vietnam. It did provide further empirical evidence of managerial coaching away from Western Country. In particular, it strengthens the theoretical evidences of the outcomes of managerial coaching under Vietnam context, in companies working in logistics and transportation industry.

Firstly, according to the research's results, more managerial coaching will lead to more employee job satisfaction and employee affective Organizational Commitment among employees working in transportation and logistics companies in Vietnam. The average score given by studied participants for managerial coaching in transportation and logistics companies is quite high (3.98) and it is suitable with the problem stating at the very beginning that due to the lack of well-educated work force, more coaching should be performed in this new industry and that Vietnam is a good environment for manager to practice managerial coaching. That is also a good and positive signal showing that managers working in transportation and logistics companies in Vietnam pay much attention to coaching their own subordinates to help them grow despite the fact that coaching is still quite new in Vietnam. Although the average score seems high, there still exist some employees who assess their direct managers with low scores of managerial coaching. It gives an implication for the organizations that it is still possible to encourage managers at all levels to perform more managerial coaching practice in order to get higher employee job satisfaction and employee affective organizational commitment.

Also, the negative relation between managerial coaching and employee turnover intention in transportation and logistics could be paid attention to. Opposite to the "easy to quit" issue of young Vietnamese employees stating in the introduction part of this theory, the average score of employee turnover intention seems not high which is just 2.88 points. There must be some reasons behind this figure such as people do not want to quit because the work itself in this new industry is considered as interesting, dynamic and full of challenges (Vietnam Ministry of Trade and Technology, 2018). Although the figure recorded for employee turnover intention is not quite high, organizations still need to lower it as the lower turnover intention is, the better it is for organizations. The research results suggested that higher managerial coaching could be a predictor for lower employee turnover intention so enhancing managerial coaching is also one of the solutions to achieve lower employee turnover intention.

In addition, managerial coaching is a process which requires the cooperation of both coach and coaches. Therefore, to facilitate the managerial coaching of managers, employees should show the cooperation with their direct managers.

Even though the results of this study are consistent with the previous literature about managerial coaching taking places in transportation and logistics companies in Vietnam, the question if managerial coaching could work in other industries should be addressed by further studies in the future. In addition, for a bigger range, it is still doubtful whether managerial coaching could work under context of other collectivistic, non-western countries which have the quite same economic situations or even less developing situation like Vietnam such as Laos, Cambodia or Myanmar. Furthermore, it is also doubtful if managerial coaching could work in some non-Western countries but with individualistic culture like Japan.

However, due to the limited time and resources, this study could not avoid some limitations. Firstly, the number of participants who participated into the study may be not big, the results of the research may become more precise if more data were collected. Besides, all the measured instruments of the surveys were answered and evaluated by employees themselves so the biases in their response could not be avoided. In addition, as this study combines all employees at any level providing that they have the direct managers and they are working in transportation and logistics companies in Vietnam, it could lead to distortion in research's results. Since each level of employees requires a different level of coaching, the result of managerial coaching could be different for employees at different levels. For the future research, the impact of managerial coaching on employee performances (suggested by Park, 2007; Kim, 2013 and some other scholars) should be studied because improving employee performance is always the important thing that all organizations are seeking for because it decides the existence of the organizations. In addition, research of managerial coaching in other kinds of companies in Vietnam should also be conducted. For example, managerial coaching study could be conducted in private sector in Vietnam due to its speedy and strong development recently.

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